

**From Empire to the War on Terror: The Instrumentalization of Human Agency in
Kamila Shamsie's *A God in Every Stone* and Fatima Bhutto's *The Runaways***

Dr. Muhammad Ilyas

Lecturer, Department of English

Khushal Khan Khattak University Karak. muhammad.ilyas@kkkuk.edu.pk

Abstract: *Instrumentalization is the treatment of someone's actions or agency as a tool/instrument for someone else's agenda. This study focuses on a parallel pattern of the West's instrumentalization of the native subjects' agency during colonial rule and the Muslims' agency in the wake of War on Terror. The study is comparative in nature highlighting the reclaim and then the instrumentalization of the protagonists' agency in Shamsie's *A God in Every Stone* and Bhutto's *The Runaways*. The study maintains that the West instrumentalizes the resistance of Pashtuns during colonial rule and the Muslims in the wake of War on Terror by turning their agency into evidence of extremism or radicalization. The West first marginalizes and force the subjects to act. Those actions are instrumented later by the western discourses to serve its narrative. The study employs Ambreen Hai's (2009) three-dimensional model of human agency for textual analysis of the novels. The model is based on three-sided nature of agency as argued by Hai in her book, *Making Words Matter: The Agency of Colonial and Postcolonial Literature*. The article concludes that Qayyum Gul, the protagonist in Shamsie's *A God in Every Stone* and Sunny (Salman Jamil), one of the protagonists in Bhutto's *The Runaways*, try to reclaim their agency; however, their agency is instrumentalized by the western discourse against them, labelling one as a savage Pashtun and the other as a terrorist.*

Keywords: *A God in Every Stone* (2014), *The Runaways* (2018), Agency, Instrumentalization, Colonial rule, The War on Terror

Introduction

Agency in everyday use is anyone's ability to perform any action as an autonomous human being. According to Ashcroft et al. (2000) in their reputed book, *Post-colonial Studies: The Key Concepts*, in postcolonial theory agency refers to the power and ability of post-colonial subjects to initiate action in such a way as to engage or resist imperial power. Many postcolonial theorists have inquired into the question of agency. In his well-known book, *Orientalism* (1978), Edward Said examines how the colonised subjects are often portrayed in the colonial discourse as inferior 'other,' which restrict their struggle and representation. In other words they are denied agency to contest colonial discourse. Fanon's work, *The Wretched of the Earth* (1961), focuses on violence as tool of resistance for liberation from colonial

oppression. The violent resistance as process of liberation can be termed as Fanon's concept of agency of the colonised. Bhabha's theorization of "The Postcolonial and the Postmodern: The Question of Agency" presented in his well-known book, *The Location of Culture* (1994), investigates the question of agency as the capacity of post-colonial subjects to act according to a decision. According to Fay and Haydon (2017), one of the key themes of Bhabha's work is to analyze whether colonised people could resist the overbearing authority of colonial discourse or not. If yes, up to what extent could they resist the colonial discourse and practice? Spivak's *Can the Subaltern Speak?* (1988), examines agency as the limits of individuals to make their own decisions and to speak for themselves in postcolonial context. Talking about the complex and confusing nature of agency in recent times, Ashcroft et al. (2000) asserts that the question of agency has been a troublesome one as the colonial discourse theory of Bhabha and Spivak depends on much of the post-structuralist position on subjectivity.

Agency, thus, is a complicated term in recent times as the contemporary theory of subjectivity questions the autonomy of individuals to initiate an action. According to Ashcroft et al. (2000), the contemporary theory of subjectivity focuses on the question whether individuals are free and autonomous in initiating an action or what they do is in some ways controlled by the ways in which their identity has been constructed. The term has become an issue as of late due to the post-structuralist theory of subjectivity. According to the theory of subjectivity, the construction of human subjectivity is based on ideology as well as language, and or discourse. Contrary to the autonomous state of individuals, post-structuralist theory of subjectivity claims that any type of action performed by a subject must be a consequence of ideology, language or discourse up to some extent (Ashcroft et al., 2000). However, many theories in which political action is of great importance ignore post-structuralist position on subjectivity in the context of individual agency. Those theories suggest that escape of the subjects from the effects of those forces that construct them is not completely impossible (Ashcroft et al., 2000).

Human agency becomes a fraught issue then because it gives rise to questions about claims and responsibility of individuals. An important question that can be asked is about the autonomy of humans and their claim of credit or responsibility for their choices and actions. Smith (1988) claims that a person is not only the actor who blindly follows "ideological scripts" but he/she is also an agent who reads them first to decide whether to insert him/herself into the script or not (p. xiii). Smith's notion of human agency foregrounds individuals as autonomous beings to decide whether to initiate an action or not. Similarly, Alidou (2005) employs the concept of agency to mean a wide range of small or large "conscious actions and initiatives" (p. 4).

Ambreen Hai (2009) presents a three-dimensional model of human agency based on three-sided nature of agency in her book, *Making Words Matter: The Agency of Colonial and Postcolonial Literature*. The first dimension of human agency according to Hai (2009) is that an agent can be an autonomous and independent individual who can choose to act independently. The second dimension is that an agent may act for another, in another's interests. Such an act is subject to another's will or intentions and the agent functions as a tool or an instrument. The third dimension is that someone who is denied agency is also an agent. Such an agent is acted upon and made into non-agents. They are left with no choice. The

researcher analyzes instrumentalization of agency by applying Hai's (2009) three-dimensional model of human agency on the protagonists as agent characters in Shamsie's *A God in Every Stone* and Bhutto's *The Runaways*.

Literature Reviews

Liaqat and Akhtar (2019) in their article, *Repression and Resistance: A Foucauldian Discourse Analysis of Power Structures in the Novel A God in Every Stone* by Kamila Shamsie, highlight various form of domination and power. The article uses Foucauldian theory of power to shed light on manifestation of dominations by foregrounding Shamsie's brilliant depiction of power-relation and colonised response to it in the text. According to the researchers, Shamsie's *A God in Every Stone* narrates two parallel set of stones side by side. On one hand it depicts women like Vivian Rose Spencer, and on the other hand it is story of two brothers, Qayyum and Najeeb and the various form of domination they encounter. The authors maintain that Shamsie portrays the manifestation of power and Resistance through social structure, historical figures, hegemonic structures, individual subjugations, and spatial domination.

Inam et al. (2020) in their article, *Colonisation and Decolonisation of the Indian Subcontinent: A Colonial Discourse Analysis of A God in Every Stone*, examines the establishment of British Empire in the Indian subcontinent through the help of colonial discourses. Using Homi K. Bhaba's theory "Of Mimicry and Man: The Ambivalence of Colonial Discourse" as theoretical framework, the article investigates the use of colonial discourses in the novel. The researchers argue that the British Empire had taken its roots in the Indian subcontinent not due to military might but because of colonial discourses. However, the anxiously repetitive nature of the same discourses gave rise to anti-colonial resistance, and ultimately to the collapse of the British Empire. Ayaz et al. (2023) in their research article, *Analyzing Kamila Shamsie's A God in Every Stone: Colonialism and Resistance*, shed light on the importance of nationalism as a serving force during independence movement in the text. The article aim to highlight the undeniable role of nationalism in the context of Caria, Armenia, and Indian subcontinent by focusing on theory of nationalism to highlight national attachment in the text. The article concludes that the nationalistic sentiments became the guiding force for these three nations to gain an autonomous nation for their people and helps to resist imperial power in shape of Persia, the British, and Ottoman Empire. Shamsie portrays how the concept of nationalism unities and motivates these three colonised nations to resist colonisers and to preserve their national heritage.

Kharal et al. (2022) in their research article, *Deconstructing the Metanarrative of Jihadism: A Postmodern Study of Fatima Bhutto's Novel The Runaways*, explore different elements that influence characters' mind towards fanaticism in the novel. By applying 'illegitimacy of totalizing narratives' by Jean-Francois Lyotard as theoretical framework, the researchers aim to find different factors behind radicalize behavior of a certain characters in novel.

Ahmad and Mustafa (2023) in their essay, *Roots of Radicalism: Analyzing post-9/11 Situation in The Runways* by Fatima Bhutto, examine lives of main characters influenced by capitalism, modernity and homelessness. In broader context, the article analyzes the novel as a contest of Islamophobia in post 9/11 West. The study has been carried out through postcolonial critique of the novel to reveal the reasons behind radicalism of the main characters.

Rabbi et al. (2023) in their article, Alienation in *The Runaways* (A Novel by Fatima Bhutto): A Psychoanalytical Reasoning for Fundamentalism and Radicalization, examine the suffering of young adults from alienation in contemporary post 9/11 situation resulting in their involvement in terrorist activities. To explore the theme of alienation from psychoanalytical perspectives, the researchers have employed Lacan's concept of other. The article investigates the possible reasons for terrorism in shape of young people's gun violence contrary to the association of fundamentalism and radicalism with religious origin.

Methodological Framework

The present study is qualitative in nature. Instrumentalization of human agency has been analyzed in Kamila Shamsie's *A God in Every Stone* and Fatima Bhutto's *The Runaways* through textual analysis. Textual analysis is a research methodology or a data gathering process for researchers to gather information about the ways other human beings are making sense of the world (Mckee, 2003). It is a research methodology that involves interpreting text data and addressing various research questions. It "allows us to see how similar or different the sense-making practices that different people use can be (Mckee, 14). Textual analysis can be applied to different types of texts, including written, visual, audio, and digital. A text is anything that we interpret or make meaning from. It can be a book, a television programme, a film, a magazine, a graffiti, an advertisement, a piece of furniture or ornament, and so on (Mckee, 2003). The methods used for textual analysis vary depending on the type of text and research question. According to Mckee (2003), "when we perform textual analysis on a text, we make an educated guess at some of the most likely interpretations that might be made of that text (p.1). The process involves selecting the text, coding the text, analyzing the text, and interpreting the text.

The present study employs Alan McKee's (2003) *Textual Analysis: A Beginner's Guide* as a methodological framework for textual analysis. McKee's book frames textual analysis as a qualitative research method to investigate how meaning is made in a context. McKee focuses on the function of texts within culture instead of just what texts say. According to McKee (2003), all texts are polysemic i.e. they are open to multiple meanings. He believes that meaning is not fixed or inherent in the text. He further asserts that the social and cultural context of both the text and the reader should be considered in textual analysis. The analysts, instead of being objective or attached, should know about their interpretive position. According to McKee, while doing textual analysis, we are not interested in deciding the right interpretation, rather, we are interested in finding out "likely interpretation" (p. 63).

Results and Discussion

Qayyum Gul, a young Pashtun living in Peshawar of colonial India, is one of the two protagonists in *A God in Every Stone*. The second protagonist is his younger brother, Najeeb Gul. Instrumentalization of agency is analyzed in this article through the first protagonist, Qayyum Gul. The plot of the novel covers the time span from 1915 to 1930. Qayyum is a Lance-Naik in 40th Pathans of British Indian Army who is discharged from the army after losing his eye in World War I while fighting on the frontline at Vipers, France. Qayyum is initially loyal subjects to the British Empire and feels proud serving the Empire. As the novel progresses, Qayyum realizes the oppression of Pashtuns at hands of the Empire. He, however,

is not a passive victim of colonial oppression; instead, being an active agent of change he tries to reclaim his agency by resisting the Empire. According to Ahmida (2005), “while the context of power affects people, human agency matters” (p. xv). Utilizing his agency to bring a change, Qayyum joins *The Khudai Khitmatgar* movement led by a Pashtun nationalist leader, Abdul Ghaffar Khan (Bacha Khan) to educate and mobilize Pashtuns against the British. His reclaim of agency leads to the massacre of unarmed Pashtun protesters on April 23, 1930 in the Street of Storytellers in Peshawar. The incident is historically known as Kissa Khwani Massacre, in which hundreds of unarmed Pashtuns were killed by the British.

In spite of losing his eye fighting ‘their’ war in World War I, Qayyum Gul, the first protagonist in *A God in Every Stone*, is still trying to serve British Empire in any way possible. He has all his loyalties with the British Empire, and cannot bear to listen anything against the Empire. “Gul is spellbound by the colonial discourses and openly exalts the superiority of British, praise their race, culture and political system in comparison to that of his own” (Inam et al., 2020, p. 286). He can be seen as a victim of colonial discourse that tried to justify colonisation of India as mission of civilizing on part of White Man’s burden. Colonial discourse, according to Ashcroft et al. (2000), is “a system of statements that can be made about colonies and colonial peoples, about colonizing powers and about the relationship between these two. It is the system of knowledge and beliefs about the world within which acts of colonisation take place” (p. 37). In Hadda Mullah’s story in the Street of Story tellers, the Story teller asks the listeners in the last couplet to join Haji Sahib Taurangzai’s jihad for independence of Pashtuns. The crowd cheers, but Qayyum doesn’t like it. As narrated in the novel, Men around Qayyum cheered, and they all repeated the last line back to the storyteller. “Rise up! Join him!” (Shamsie, 2014, p. 143). But Qayyum turned away and went from there briskly. Qayyum has been portrayed in the beginning of the novel as a non-agent in terms of resisting the Empire. Unable to realize the oppression of the Empire, he has been denied agency by colonial discourse. Colonial discourse mainly operated as an effective instrument of power in the colonial era (Ashcroft et al., 2000). However, his friend, Sepoy Kalam Khan makes him realize the oppression of Pashtuns at hands of the Empire.

Kalam Khan and Qayyum are close friends who had been together in the same trench in World War I. Kalam had saved Qayyum’s life at Vipers, France. He serves as foil to Qayyum in the novel to make him reclaim his agency. Kalam’s resign from the British Indian Army during World War I gives rise to many questions in the mind of Qayyum. He is informed of his friend’s coming back to Peshawar through a short letter from Kalam. He fears that his friend might have either lost a limb or an eye because these were the only reasons he could be discharged from the army, like Qayyum himself who had lost his eye. However, when Qayyum visits him in his village he finds that Kalam has lost neither a limb nor an eye rather he has deserted army. Kalam then tells him that the English have stopped recruiting Pashtuns. The reason according to Kalam is that when we are asked to fight our fellow Muslims, then we mutiny and “too many [of us] desert” (Shamsie, 2014, p. 147). The passage suggests oppression of the Empire towards Pashtuns making them fight their Muslim brothers of the Ottoman Empire. Oppression of the Empire in colonial India is further revealed when telling Qayyum, Kalam adds that you are supposed to feel proud of yourself that you are from such an ethnic group who will not kill their Muslim brother “at the command of their oppressors” (Shamsie,

2014, p. 147). Serving as a foil to Qayyum, Kalam reveals his intentions to go to his mother's tribe and join Haji Sahib's jihad for independence. Qayyum, as a victim of colonial discourse opposes the idea and stops Kalam from going to his mother's tribe. The colonised agency of Qayyum has been revealed here who is not willing to take a stand against his oppressors. In other words, he has been denied agency by colonial discourse. However, revealing the double standards of the West, Kalam shames Qayyum by saying that you are willing to fight for the English who are trying to defend their land against the invaders, but when your own people want the same, you "turn the invaders into your beloved" (Shamsie, 2014, p. 147). Qayyum's turning the English invaders into his beloved reveals that he has been made into a non-agent as colonised subject of the British Empire. He cannot feel oppression of the Empire the way other Pashtuns feel it. Colonial discourse has denied him agency making him bear the yoke of the Empire happily. Colonial discourses are the necessary ingredient of the project of colonisation and "are used to inculcate into the natives of the colonies the idea that it is justified to colonize them and they should accept their inferior status" (Inam et al, 2020, p. 283).

Qayyum finally realizes that Kalam was right asking him to resist the Empire. Sitting at his father's desk as a letter writer, an Englishwoman catches his glance who passed in a little distance. As narrated in the novel, it reminds him Kalam's words who often mocked Qayyum for sitting under a tree thinking about his buffalo horn as his inheritance while an Englishwoman walked as freely in the street of Peshawar "as if she had more right to it than any man of Peshawar" (Shamsie, 2014, p. 163). Realizing the oppression of the Empire, Qayyum decides to resist the Empire as an agent of change. As an autonomous individual, no more controlled by the colonial discourse, he decides to join the non-violent movement of Ghaffar Khan (Bacha Khan). In the chapter named as 'March 1916,' the loyalties of Qayyum have been depicted as 'changed'. Initially his loyalties were with the Empire, but after meeting Ghaffar Khan, he decides to join his movement as an autonomous agent of change.

Qayyum's reclaim of agency is evident through his reply to his brother's letter revealing his brother's victimization to the colonial discourse. Najeeb Gul, as Indian Assistant at Peshawar Museum writes to Qayyum from Taxila while working on in archeological site. Admiring the English, he writes that he is grateful to the English for putting a spade in his hands and allowing him to know his "own history" (Shamsie, 2014, p. 228). Qayyum's reply to Najeeb's letter shows his reclaim of agency to counter colonial discourse regarding colonisation of India as a civilizing mission. He is no more living under the false claims of the colonisers the way his brother is still living. Therefore he writes back to his brother (Shamsie's way of writing back to the West):

Of all the fantastic tales you've ever told none is more fantastic than that of the kindly English who dig up our treasures because they want you to know your own history. Your museums are all part of their Civilising Mission, their White Man's Burden, their moral justification for what they have done here (Shamsie, 2014, p. 232).

The passage reveals the reality of colonial discourse which represented colonisation as a civilizing mission. The reality was to plunder all the wealth from the colonised lands. Qayyum, as an agent of change, resists colonial discourse trying to justify colonisation of India. As Najeeb's loyalties are still with the English being a victim of colonial discourse, Qayyum further adds that our numbers are increasing and while I celebrate this thought I fear for you

because one day you will realize that you are just a subject, “a yoked Pashtun” who is mistaken to think that the yoke is “silk cravat” which you will have to wear like your turban all your life (Shamsie, 2014, p. 232). It shows Qayyum’s realization of being yoked for a long time. Once realized that the yoke is not a silk cravat as the English had been giving this impression, Qayyum starts participating in struggle for independence.

Qayyum Gul decides to participate in the protest against the Empire in the Street of Storytellers on 23rd April 1930. As Fanon (1961) notes that “the great figures of the colonised people are always those who led the national resistance to invasion,” Qayyum too stood in front of the English’s guns (p. 69). While Fanon believes in violent resistance, Qayyum was unarmed as the protest was a part of the non-violent movement for independence from the British Empire. As narrated in the novel, for the first time in his life Qayyum came to know such clarity of purpose while he was standing on the front line in the Street of Storytellers “facing the soldiers with bayonets at the ready” (Shamsie, 2014, p. 253). The peaceful protest by Pashtuns later turns into the massacre of unarmed Pashtuns when the English open fire from machine guns. Hundreds of Pashtuns are butchered in the Street of Storytellers in response to their reclaim of agency.

Applying the second aspect of Hai’s (2009) model of human agency i.e. an agent functioning as a tool or an instrument on Qayyum’s reclaim of agency, it can be concluded that Qayyum’s agency and agency of other Pashtuns protesting peacefully is used by the English against them by opening fire on them from machine guns. They are still being called ‘savages’ by the English as they were called in the beginning of the novel. Talking about the only English soldier who died in the incident, Mr. Forbes tells Miss Spencer as narrated in the novel that the “savages” did set him on fire. Miss Spencer asks whether he was still alive. Mr. Forbes tells her that he was probably not alive but it does not matter whether he was alive or not. Miss Spencer then tells him that you mean to say that the only English soldier who died “was killed by our armoured cars” (Shamsie, 2014, p. 304). Hundreds of unarmed Pashtuns have been killed by the English, yet the word ‘savages’ is used by Mr. Forbes for the Pashtuns instrumentalizing Pashtuns’ agency against them. In other words, Qayyum’s agency is used as tool or an instrument by the British Empire.

Similarly, Sunny’s agency, one of the protagonists in Fatima Bhutto’s *The Runaways*, has also been instrumentalized by the Western discourse against him. Bhutto’s *The Runaways* is a story of three teenagers who join a jihadi organization, the Ummah Movement, in 2016-17. The three main characters are Sunny (Salman Jamil), an Indian Muslim living in Portsmouth, England; Monty (Mustafa), a rich Pakistani teenager living in Karachi; and Anita Rose (Layla), a poor Christian girl from Karachi. Sunny feels marginalized and humiliated in British society on the basis of his Muslim identity. Oz (Ozair), his charismatic cousin, after his return from Syria as jihadist, brainwashes Sunny to join jihad. As soon as Sunny lands in Iraq, Oz stops responding to his messages and himself stays back in England. Similarly, Monty and Anita too join the Ummah Movement. Anita joins it as Layla when her illicit video gets viral after being forced by her brother to be with a rich businessman. She enjoys an important position in the Ummah Movement to add glamour to jihad through her video messages. Monty joins it in love of Layla, to find her. The action of the latter half of the novel takes place in Iraq in shape of a long journey taken by Sunny and Monty from Mosul to Nineveh as guerrilla

warfare. Back in England, Oz starts running a newsletter with the name of “Reforming Radicals” from American platform. In reaction to Oz’s newsletter, Sunny decides to be a hardcore jihadist and starts posting pro-jihad pictures and videos.

Sunny, a young British born Indian Muslim living in Portsmouth, England joins a militant group in Iraq, the Ummah Movement in 2016-17. He tries to reclaim his agency by joining the Ummah Movement to claim his place and voice in the world following his social marginalization in the Western world during the second decade of twenty-first century. He suffers marginalization and othering in Western society because of his religion in the wake of War on Terror in 2014-15. Even the kids he has grown up with do not want to have anything to do with him because of his Muslim identity. As narrated in the novel, “The kids he had grown up with – white boys like Shane and Ben – didn’t want anything to do with him. They still hung out with the Asians, with Mickey and Raj and those guys, but not with the Muslims any more” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 73). The passage shows ‘othering’ of Muslims in England on the basis of their religion, as Shane and Ben still hung out with other Indians, but not with the Muslims anymore. Although, he is a British citizen, he is always given this impression that he is an immigrant and destroying Europe. He liked Stefan, his gym instructor, for the reason that he never talked to him like that. As narrated in the novel, “When they hung out at the gym, Stefan never talked about the news or how migration was ruining Europe, like every other Whitey did” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 45).

Sunny is also stereotyped in the Western society on the basis of his religion and color. As narrated in the novel, “Ben might not have wanted anything to do with Sunny, calling him a sand nigger, a Taliban, whatever they called any proud man of colour” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 75). He faces severe hatred in the Western society on the basis of his religion. As narrated in the novel, “After that attack in France, an old woman in curlers spat at Sunny on the bus. I didn’t do it, he wanted to tell her, burning with shame” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 267). As narrated, the conductor saw the whole thing in his mirror, smiled at Sunny sympathetically, and said, “She thinks I did 9/11. Spits at everyone.’ The conductor was a brother, like Sunny. Brown as brown can be. The old woman looked at Sunny as if she knew him. As if she knew who Sunny was and hated him for it” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 267). The passage shows the kind of hatred Sunny and other Muslims in the West are facing on the basis of their religion. Islam as a marginalized religion has to suffer the consequence of an attack anywhere in the Western world. The Muslims are being spat on, stereotyped as Taliban, and even abused. They have been denied agency to present their point of view or resist their marginalization on the basis of their color and religion. As non-agents, they have to suffer stereotyping of the West.

An instance of Muslims’ ‘othering’ as portrayed in the novel is through division of the East and the West. Said (1978) uses the term ‘Orientalism’ to refer to the collective colonial discourses in which the West represents the ‘Orient’ (the native of the colonies) as uncivilized and backward. Said is of the view that ‘Orientalism constructs binary division’ between ‘Occident’ (the West) and the ‘Orient’ (the other). Both are described in opposition to each other. Analyzing Said’s *Orientalism*, Inam et al. (2020) notes that in colonial discourses the West is depicted as the place of knowledge, learning, and civilization. On the other hand, the Orient is described as the very opposite of these qualities and the centre of ignorance, violence, and lust” (p. 284). The division of the world into West and non-West was done by colonial

discourse attaching superiority with the West. This division can be observed even in the twenty-first century marking colonial legacies in one way or the other. Sunny, being a British citizen is considered uncivilized and inferior to Europeans on the basis of his religion and color. After smashing Ben's jaws into the table, Sunny has been called by the headmistress at St Thomas'. Although, Sunny pleads that "He'd humiliated Sunny for years, saying he should pack his shit and go back to Pakistan – where Sunny was not even from – and stop sucking England dry" (Bhutto, 2018, p. 268). As narrated in the novel, the headmistress sneered like she couldn't hear him and told him that the place you are living in is Europe. She further added that "we are civilized here, we are educated. We do not assault people over an insult" (Bhutto, 2018, p. 268). 'We are civilized here' reminds Said's (1978) postcolonial theorization of the West's distorted image of the East as exotic 'others' who are always considered uncivilized. What will be the headmistress's stance on 'the insult of 9/11' which turned the Muslim world upside down in contrast to her claim of being 'civilized' who do not assault people over an insult?'

As a result of 'othering' on the basis of his Muslim identity, Sunny faces severe alienation in Western society. Oxford Dictionary (2005) defines alienation as "the feeling that you do not belong in a particular group." The first instance of Sunny's alienation and identity crisis in Portsmouth has been portrayed in the novel through his confusion and emptiness. As narrated in the novel, Sunny felt like he had been waiting all his life for someone to see him and to know the confusion and emptiness he is going through. He had been waiting for someone to meet him and lift him from "his troubled self" (Bhutto, 2018, p. 43). The passage shows that he feels troubled in the society he is living in because he is looked at as other on the basis of his Muslim identity after 9/11 attacks and subsequent War on Terror. Similarly, as narrated in the novel, Sunny would go for long walks moving around Portsmouth in an attempt to find refuge in what seemed to him to be only "a wasteland" in shape of a town occupied by forgotten people (Bhutto, 2018, p. 51). Being 'other,' he does not have any self, identity, and purpose. He is in a state of finding refuge. That's why he blames his father for not staying in India with his own people in his own country instead of coming to England where they are "nobodies" (Bhutto, 2018, p. 51). Although he is a British citizen, he lacks the sense of place in England as his country, as he has been marginalized. This is the reason he wishes his father had stayed in his native country, India, so that he would not have been an 'other' there. This feeling of being nobody in the Western society was extremely torturous for him. The wanting of being important had become a severe ache for him. As narrated in the novel, most mornings Sunny woke up and found it difficult to breathe as he wished so much to be seen and known. It was such a severe wanting that it had become an ache which seemed to be stiched across his skin. He felt that if acted rashly "he would be torn apart" (Bhutto, 2018, p. 77). Such alienated and marginalized people are vulnerable to an easy brainwash and this is what happens to Sunny too. Sunny starts questioning his reclaim of agency.

Another instance of Sunny's alienation and marginalization as portrayed in the novel is that he cannot see any future in the Western world. As narrated in the novel, "Sunny couldn't see any future. The walls around Portsmouth had never felt so high, he never imagined he could scale them" (Bhutto, 2018, p. 73). He wishes to run away, but the walls of being 'other' around him are so high that he cannot scale them. Similarly, he felt like in need of an armour against the stereotyping he faced on the basis of his Muslim identity. As narrated in the novel, he felt

that “How long must a man walk through this city with no armour? His body was a naked wound in those days, his heart beat ferociously beneath his breast, so aware was he of being unprotected, so alone and afraid” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 52). The passage shows that Sunny felt unprotected, alone and afraid in the Western world due to his ‘othering.’ That’s why he does not agree with his father when his father is feeling proud of being a British citizen. Sunny’s harsh attitude towards his father can be seen in the passage when they were sitting together at a café in Portsmouth. As narrated in the novel, Sunny shouts at his father saying that “This life here? That hanky? That accent of yours? It’s a joke!” It was an oblivion worse than death to be no one but Sulaiman Jamil’s son. A nothing. A nobody whose life was marked only by its unremarkability” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 277). These passages show that Sunny suffered from severe alienation and identity crisis due to his ‘othering’ in the Western society on the basis of his Muslim identity in the second decade of twenty first century. However, being an agent of change he tries to reclaim his agency by resisting the Western world.

As a marginalized subject in the Western world, Sunny is not a passive victim but tries to reclaim his agency. An agent can be an autonomous and independent individual who can choose to act independently (Hai, 2009). Sunny tries to reclaim agency by joining a militant group in Iraq, the Umma Movement, as a notion of his resistance towards his ‘othering’ by the West and to claim his place and importance in the world. An alienated Sunny needed a spark from somewhere to claim his place in the world, which he got in shape of his charismatic cousin, Oz. Oz has just returned from Syria and he could convince Sunny that jihad is the only way he can make himself known. As narrated in the novel, Sunny has never felt he belonged in Portsmouth throughout his life. He could never be understood by Ben and his other fellow neighbors. He knew that no one is able to see through the fog around him to feel the pain, loneliness, and confusion. “No one until Oz” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 101). After meeting Ozair, Sunny decides to reclaim his agency against his ‘othering’ and marginalization in the Western world. When Sunny decides to join the Ummah Movement to reclaim his agency, he makes his comparison with his father and thinks that his father was just a sad, old man the world had spat out. Talking about his self, Sunny thinks that he is going to be different who would be respected by people. People “would remember him. Recognize him” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 102).

Ultimately he reclaims his agency and joins the Ummah Movement, an Islamist jihadist organization in Iraq. Applying the second aspect of Hai’s (2009) model of human agency i.e. agent being acted upon, or agency used against the agent, it can be noticed that Sunny’s agency is instrumentalized against him. As soon as he lands in Iraq as a jihadist believed to be fighting against the West, Oz, his cousin, stops responding to his emails and text messages. Oz makes all the arrangement for Sunny to send him to jihad in Iraq; and later the same Oz, representing the West in the novel, is sitting on the stage of the West criticizing the actions of people like Sunny. As narrated in the novel, Oz is interviewed on CNN dressed up in a cream-coloured suit as a reformer “sitting on a stage, sponsored by the World Bank” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 226). It is exactly like the West first oppress, marginalize, and ‘other’ the Muslims; and when the marginalized try to reclaim their agency by fighting against the West, they are labelled as radicals and terrorists. It is exactly the way Oz has been introduced by the interviewer to have gone from England to Syria and back again to Europe. From hate to acceptance. From radical fundamentalist, which can be also called from “terrorist to reformer” (Bhutto, 2018, p. 225).

Sunny's reclaim of agency adds one more number to 'radical Muslims' as the West looks at the Muslims; and places him in the list of terrorists as seen by Western perspective.

Conclusion

Analysis of Qayyum Gul's agency in Shamsie's *A God in Every Stone* and Sunny's agency in Bhutto's *The Runaways* reveals the West's pattern of instrumentalizing human agency did not change since colonial era to the War on Terror. The protagonists in the selected novels are seen as 'other' on the basis of their race, nationality and religion leading to their marginalization and alienation. However, they are not passive victims, rather, being agent characters, they try to reclaim their agency. They reclaim their agency by resisting colonial power structures through acts of resistance, protest, speech, and writing as autonomous individuals. The study reveals that though the protagonists act; yet, their agency is instrumentalized by the dominant discourses of the West against them, labelling one as a savage Pashtun and the other as a terrorist.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends that other novels or literary texts may also be explored to understand how other writers tackle the instrumentalization of Pashtuns' and the Muslims' agency in the wake of War on Terror.

References

- Ahmad, H., & Mustafa, S. (2023). The roots of radicalism: Analyzing post-9/11 situation in *The Runways* by Fatima Bhutto. *City University Research Journal of Literature and Linguistics*, 6(2), 58-78.
- Ahmida, A. A. (2005). *Forgotten voices: Power and agency in colonial and postcolonial Libya*. Routledge.
- Alidou, O. D. (2005). *Engaging modernity: Muslim women and the politics of agency in postcolonial Niger*. The University of Wisconsin Press.
- Ashcroft, B., Griffiths, G., & Tiffin, H. (2000). *Post-colonial studies: The key concepts*. Routledge.
- Bhutto, F. (2018). *The Runaways*. Penguin.
- Fay, S., & Haydon, L. (2017). An analysis of Homi K. Bhabha's *The Location of Culture*. Routledge.
- Hai, A. (2009). *Making words matter: Agency of colonial and postcolonial literature*. Ohio University Press.
- Inam, U., Andama, G., & Nawaz, A. (2020). Colonisation and decolonisation of the Indian subcontinent: A colonial discourse analysis of *A God in Every Stone*. *Liberal Arts and Social Sciences International Journal*, 4(1), 282-292. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47264/idea.lassij/4.1.24>

- Kharal, Q. A., Naseem, S., & Muhammad H. (2022). Deconstructing the metanarrative of jihadism: A postmodern study of Fatima Bhutto's Novel *The Runaways*. *Journal of English Language Literature and Education*, 3(4), 36-53.
- Liaqat, Q. U. A., & Akhtar, R. (2019). Repression and resistance: A Foucauldian discourse analysis of power structures in the novel *A God in Every Stone* by Kamila Shamsie. *Journal of Research in Humanities*, 55(1), 1-16.
- Mckee, A. (2003). *Textual analysis: A beginner's guide*. Sage Publications.
- Rabbi, A., Hassan, S., & Kurd. S. A. (2023). Alienation in *The Runaways* (A novel by Fatima Bhutto): A psychoanalytical reasoning for fundamentalism and radicalization. *Al-Qantara*, 9(1).
- Shamsie, K. (2014). *A god in every stone*. Bloomsbury.
- Smith, P. (1988). *Discerning the subject*. University of Minnesota Press.